

LETTER TO EDITOR

Neurological Manifestations of COVID-19 Patients and Management

Abdur Rahman¹, Ivan David Lozada-Martinez², Sabrina Rahman³, AHM Ataullah⁴, Karen Muñoz-Baez⁵, Luis Rafael Moscote-Salazar⁶ and Moshir Rahman^{7*}

¹Honorary Medical Officer, Dhaka Medical College and Hospital, Dhaka, Bangladesh

²Medical and Surgical Research Center, University of Cartagena, Cartagena, Colombia

³Department of Public Health, Independent University- Bangladesh, Dhaka, Bangladesh

⁴Medical Officer, Sher-E-Bangla Medical College Hospital, Barishal, Bangladesh

⁵Colombian Clinical Research Group in Neurocritical Care, University of Cartagena, Cartagena, Colombia

⁶Center for Biomedical Research (CIB), Faculty of Medicine, University of Cartagena, Cartagena, Colombia

⁷Colombia

⁷Neurosurgery Department, Holy Family Red Crescent Medical College, Dhaka, Bangladesh

SARS-CoV-2 was first observed in Wuhan, China, and quickly spread throughout the world, proclaimed as a pandemic by WHO. Most reported cases have respiratory symptoms, but many cases are seen with neurological signs as initial or related presentations [1].

With the flow of time, massive data on various aspects of the disease, such as manifestations, pathology, transmission, prevention, and management strategies, has begun to emerge [2,3]. Myalgia and fatigue, dizziness, headache, anosmia, ageusia, and altered mental status are relatively common in Covid patients with preexisting comorbidities [4]. Also, known risk factors associated with neurological symptoms include advanced age, heart failure, coronary artery disease, hypertension, dyslipidemia, diabetes mellitus, obesity, chronic obstructive pulmonary disease, asthma, chronic renal failure, liver disease, malignancy, smoking, immunosuppression [5].

Aerosol droplets penetrate the nasal mucosa of COVID-infected patients; travel through the cribriform palate into the Central Nervous System (CNS). Then it spread to the CNS through the direct invasion of the virus and produces neurological signs [6]. In up to 25% of COVID-19 cases, manifestations of Central Nervous System (CNS) involvement have been reported [4]. Other neuroinvasion mechanisms involve transsynaptic transfer via infected neurons, direct entry through the olfactory nerve, infected vascular endothelium, or leukocyte migration through the blood-brain barrier, cytokine storm, immunological causes, hypoxic brain injuries, often several drugs side effects are also identified [6]. In a retrospective study of the clinical characteristics of 113 COVID-19 patients from China, Chen, et al. [7] discovered hypoxic encephalopathy in 20 of them. Moriguchi, et al. [8] from Japan reported the first confirmed case of COVID-19-associated viral meningoencephalitis. Several cases of CVST associated with COVID-19 have been reported. The increased risk of arterial ischemic stroke or CVST in SARS-CoV-2 infection suggests a pro-coagulant state, which could be caused by either blood flow stasis, particularly in critically ill and immobilized patients, or hypercoagulability [9]. According to a Bangladeshi study, the most common neurological diagnosis in the Covid-19 was stroke [29(54.71%)], subdural empyema [1(1.88%)], meningo-encephalitis [15(65.21%)],

***Corresponding author**

Moshir Rahman, Department of Neurosurgery, Holy Family Red Crescent Medical College, Dhaka, Bangladesh

E-mail: dr.tutul@yahoo.com

DOI: 10.37871/jbres1249

Submitted: 25 May 2021

Accepted: 25 May 2021

Published: 27 May 2021

Copyright: © 2021 Rahman A, et al. Distributed under Creative Commons CC-BY 4.0

OPEN ACCESS

MEDICAL GROUP

NEUROLOGY | NEUROLOGICAL DISORDERS | NEUROSURGERY
PUBLIC HEALTH

VOLUME: 2 ISSUE: 5

Guillain-Barre syndrome [3(5.66%)], and so on [10]. A systematic analysis of 554 COVID-19 patients revealed that the mean prevalence of headache was 8% (95% CI 5.7-10.2%), and the prevalence of dizziness was reported to be between 7 and 9.4% [11]. Cohort study-reporting of a stroke in 2-6% of patients diagnosed with COVID-19 [11]. Stroke identified with a pro-inflammatory hypercoagulable state with elevated D-dimer, ferritin, and C-reactive protein.

Management during pandemic [12]:

- Routine COVID-19 antiviral management, if indicated.
- Symptomatic Supportive treatment of headache, neuropathic pain, and anxiety.
- Management of risk factors.
- Antiviral agents, anti-thrombotic and anti-inflammatory medications are used as an indication.
- Stroke therapy with the possible use of Intravenous Thrombolysis (TPA) or Endovascular Treatment (EVT) with mechanical thrombectomy in COVID-19 patients.
- Steroids, IV immunoglobulins (later).
- Selective cytokine blockade with inhibition of anakinra, tocilizumab, or Janus Kinase (JAK).
- Some antiviral and CNS drugs show drug interactions, so the risk-benefit should be measured before prescribing.
- The introduction of the protection bundle advocated by the Society of Critical Care Medicine (SCCM) in its management of the ICU shows benefits [13].
- Expert consensus statements from the European Academy of Neurology (EAN) indicate a strong response rate to direct neurologists [14].

COVID-19 can cause a wide range of neurological manifestations. Prompt recognition and treatment will help to reduce its complications. Although neurological manifestations are common in severe cases, patients with pure neurological manifestations at the onset of COVID-19 illness should be treated with caution.

References

1. Jiang F, Deng L, Zhang L, Cai Y, Cheung CW, Xia Z. Review of the Clinical Characteristics of Coronavirus Disease 2019 (COVID-19). *J Gen Intern Med.* 2020 May;35(5):1545-1549. doi: 10.1007/s11606-020-05762-w. Epub 2020 Mar 4. PMID: 32133578; PMCID: PMC7088708.

2. Di Gennaro F, Pizzol D, Marotta C, Antunes M, Raccaluto V, Veronese N, Smith L. Coronavirus Diseases (COVID-19) Current Status and Future Perspectives: A Narrative Review. *Int J Environ Res Public Health.* 2020 Apr 14;17(8):2690. doi: 10.3390/ijerph17082690. PMID: 32295188; PMCID: PMC7215977.

3. Tu H, Tu S, Gao S, Shao A, Sheng J. The epidemiological and clinical features of COVID-19 and lessons from this global infectious public health event. *Journal of Infection.* 2020 Apr 18. doi: 10.1016/j.jinf.2020.04.011

4. Mao L, Jin H, Wang M, Hu Y, Chen S, He Q, Chang J, Hong C, Zhou Y, Wang D, Miao X, Li Y, Hu B. Neurologic Manifestations of Hospitalized Patients With Coronavirus Disease 2019 in Wuhan, China. *JAMA Neurol.* 2020 Jun 1;77(6):683-690. doi: 10.1001/jamaneurol.2020.1127. PMID: 32275288; PMCID: PMC7149362.

5. Tsvigoulis G, Palaioimou L, Katsanos AH, Caso V, Köhrmann M, Molina C, Cordonnier C, Fischer U, Kelly P, Sharma VK, Chan AC, Zand R, Sarraj A, Schellinger PD, Voumvourakis KI, Grigoriadis N, Alexandrov AV, Tsioudras S. Neurological manifestations and implications of COVID-19 pandemic. *Ther Adv Neurol Disord.* 2020 Jun 9;13:1756286420932036. doi: 10.1177/1756286420932036. PMID: 32565914; PMCID: PMC7284455.

6. Orsini A, Corsi M, Santangelo A, Riva A, Peroni D, Foadelli T, Savasta S, Striano P. Challenges and management of neurological and psychiatric manifestations in SARS-CoV-2 (COVID-19) patients. *Neurol Sci.* 2020 Sep;41(9):2353-2366. doi: 10.1007/s10072-020-04544-w. Epub 2020 Aug 6. PMID: 32767055; PMCID: PMC7410516.

7. Chen T, Wu D, Chen H, Yan W, Yang D, Chen G, Ma K, Xu D, Yu H, Wang H, Wang T, Guo W, Chen J, Ding C, Zhang X, Huang J, Han M, Li S, Luo X, Zhao J, Ning Q. Clinical characteristics of 113 deceased patients with coronavirus disease 2019: retrospective study. *BMJ.* 2020 Mar 26;368:m1091. doi: 10.1136/bmj.m1091. Erratum in: *BMJ.* 2020 Mar 31;368:m1295. PMID: 32217556; PMCID: PMC7190011.

8. Moriguchi T, Harii N, Goto J, Harada D, Sugawara H, Takamino J, Ueno M, Sakata K, Kondo K, Myose N, Nakao A, Takeda M, Haro H, Inoue O, Suzuki-Inoue K, Kubokawa K, Ogihara S, Sasaki T, Kinouchi H, Kojin H, Ito M, Onishi H, Shimizu T, Sasaki Y, Enomoto N, Ishihara H, Furuya S, Yamamoto T, Shimada S. A first case of meningitis/encephalitis associated with SARS-Coronavirus-2. *Int J Infect Dis.* 2020 May;94:55-58. doi: 10.1016/j.ijid.2020.03.062. Epub 2020 Apr 3. PMID: 32251791; PMCID: PMC7195378.

9. Naeimi R, Ghasemi-Kasman M. Update on cerebrovascular manifestations of COVID-19. *Neurol Sci.* 2020 Dec;41(12):3423-3435. doi: 10.1007/s10072-020-04837-0. Epub 2020 Oct 20. PMID: 33083934; PMCID: PMC7574669.

10. Mohammad EH, Md Azharul H, Md Badrul A, Md Abdullah Y, Rajib NC, Mohammad QD. Neurological Manifestations of COVID-19 patients: An updated review and observations of Covid patients in the National Institute of Neurosciences and Hospital, Dhaka, Bangladesh. *Journal of Bangladesh College of Physicians and Surgeons.* 122-132. doi: 10.3329/jbcps.v38i0.47869.

11. Zhou Z, Kang H, Li S, Zhao X. Understanding the neurotropic characteristics of SARS-CoV-2: from neurological manifestations of COVID-19 to potential neurotropic mechanisms. *J Neurol.* 2020 Aug;267(8):2179-2184. doi: 10.1007/s00415-020-09929-7. Epub 2020 May 26. PMID: 32458193; PMCID: PMC7249973.

12. Ng Kee Kwong KC, Mehta PR, Shukla G, Mehta AR. COVID-19, SARS and MERS: A neurological perspective. *J Clin Neurosci.* 2020 Jul;77:13-16. doi: 10.1016/j.jocn.2020.04.124. Epub 2020 May 5. PMID: 32417124; PMCID: PMC7198407.

13. Pun BT, Balas MC, Barnes-Daly MA, Thompson JL, Aldrich JM, Barr J, Byrum D, Carson SS, Devlin JW, Engel HJ, Esbrook CL, Hargett KD, Harmon L, Hielsberg C, Jackson JC, Kelly TL, Kumar V, Millner L, Morse A, Perme CS, Posa PJ, Puntillo KA, Schweickert WD, Stollings JL, Tan A, D'Agostino McGowan L, Ely EW. Caring for Critically Ill Patients with the ABCDEF Bundle: Results of the ICU Liberation Collaborative in Over 15,000 Adults. *Crit Care Med.* 2019 Jan;47(1):3-14. doi: 10.1097/CCM.00000000000003482. PMID: 30339549; PMCID: PMC6298815.

14. von Oertzen TJ, Macerollo A, Leone MA, Beghi E, Crean M, Oztuk S, Bassetti C, Twardzik A, Bereczki D, Di Liberto G, Helbok R, Oreja-Guevara C, Pisani A, Sauerbier A, Sellner J, Soffietti R, Zedde M, Bianchi E, Bodini B, Cavallieri F, Campiglio L, Maia LF, Priori A, Rakusa M, Taba P, Moro E, Jenkins TM; EANcore COVID-19 task force. EAN consensus statement for management of patients with neurological diseases during the COVID-19 pandemic. *Eur J Neurol.* 2021 Jan;28(1):7-14. doi: 10.1111/ene.14521. Epub 2020 Oct 15. PMID: 33058321; PMCID: PMC7675361.

How to cite this article: Rahman A, Lozada-Martinez ID, Rahman S, Atallah AHM, Muñoz-Baez K, Moscote-Salazar LR, Rahman M. Neurological Manifestations of COVID-19 Patients and Management. *J Biomed Res Environ Sci.* 2021 May 27; 2(5): 406-407. doi: 10.37871/jbres1249, Article ID: JBRES1249